

Scurvy during Thomas Stevens' voyage to India (1579)

by Harri Hemilä

Thomas Stevens, a Jesuit, was the first Englishman to travel to India. During the voyage, several passengers suffered from scurvy, an illness that Stevens described in a letter to his father. This document contains an extract from the letter in which the symptoms of scurvy are described.

The letter (1579) was first published in Richard Hakluyt's *Principal Navigations* (1589):

https://archive.org/details/bim_early-english-books-1475-1640_the-principall-navigatio_hakluyt-richard_1589_0/page/160/mode/2up

https://archive.org/details/bim_early-english-books-1475-1640_the-principall-navigatio_hakluyt-richard_1589/page/160/mode/2up

https://archive.org/details/cihm_35668/page/n178/mode/2up

and in a later republication vol. VI (1904):

<https://archive.org/details/in.gov.ignca.21195/page/377/mode/2up>

<https://archive.org/details/in.ernet.dli.2015.89115/page/n403/mode/2up>

<https://archive.org/details/in.ernet.dli.2015.106881/page/n411/mode/2up>

<https://archive.org/details/principalnavigat06hakl/page/376/mode/2up>

And later in *English Garner* vol. I by Edward Arber (1877):

<https://archive.org/details/englishgarnering01arbeuoft/page/130/mode/2up>

<https://archive.org/details/anenglishgarneri01arbeuoft/page/130/mode/2up>

<https://archive.org/details/anenglishgarner02unkngoog/page/130/mode/2up>

<https://archive.org/details/in.ernet.dli.2015.183931/page/n127/mode/2up>

and *English Garner* (1903):

https://archive.org/details/b24871503_0001/page/152/mode/2up

The 1589 and 1877 versions are available at Zenodo along with this document.

More recently the letter (1579) was republished in:

Southwood, J. (1924). Thomas Stephens, S. J., the First Englishman in India. *Bulletin of the School of Oriental Studies, University of London*, 3(2), 231–240.
<https://www.jstor.org/stable/607122>

Yellow is used to indicate more important sections such as the symptoms of scurvy.

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<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/?term=hemila+h+vitamin>

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17085738> Reports on scurvy uploaded to Zenodo by Hemilä

The earliest recorded outbreak of scurvy on a long sea voyage seems to have occurred during Vasco da Gama's first voyage to India (1497-1499).¹ Thereafter, the disease afflicted vast numbers of sailors throughout the Age of Sail.^{2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7} In the English Navy, the incidence of scurvy declined dramatically at the end of the eighteenth century, when lime and lemon juice were made obligatory for seamen.^{8, 9}

In his authoritative book "*The History of Scurvy and Vitamin C*", Kenneth Carpenter (1986; p.3)³ summarized the letter of Thomas Stevens as follows:

In 1579, Thomas Stevens, who was a passenger on one of the regular voyages from Lisbon to Goa wrote home:

... by reason of the long navigation, and want of food and water, they fall into sundry diseases, their gums wax great, and swell, and they are fain to cut them away, their legs swell, and all the body becometh sore, and so benumbed, that they can not stir hand nor foot, and so they die for weakness, other fall into fluxes and agues, and die thereby ... ; yet though we had more than one hundred and fifty sick, there died not past seven and twenty; which loss they esteemed not much in respect of other times.

On this voyage they were 202 days at sea, and did not call at Madagascar. A paymaster's report from Goa in 1634 states that of 5,000 soldiers embarking from Lisbon in the previous five years, less than one-half survived the voyage. This was due, in part, to shipwrecks as well as to sickness.

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- 1 Scurvy during Vasco da Gama's first voyage (1497-1499).
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17781205>
<https://www.gutenberg.org/ebooks/46440>
 - 2 Lind J (1772) A Treatise on the Scurvy.
<https://archive.org/details/treatiseonscurvy1772lind/page/n5/mode/2up>
<https://wellcomecollection.org/works/r7fpbavt>
 - 3 Kenneth J Carpenter (1986) The History of Scurvy and Vitamin C: The explorers' sickness; p.1-28.
<https://www.cambridge.org/fi/universitypress/subjects/history/history-medicine/history-scurvy-and-vitamin-c>
 - 4 Scurvy during Magellan's voyage around the world (1519-1522)
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18001193>
<https://www.gutenberg.org/ebooks/42884>
<https://www.gutenberg.org/ebooks/74723>
 - 5 Scurvy on John Davis' voyage (1591-1593).
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17884408>
 - 6 Scurvy during Richard Hawkins' voyage (1593).
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18001137>
<https://www.gutenberg.org/ebooks/57502>
 - 7 Scurvy on Anson's voyage round the world (1740-1744).
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17397300>
<https://www.gutenberg.org/ebooks/16611>
<https://www.gutenberg.org/ebooks/47130>
 - 8 Budd G (1840) Scurvy.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17455962>
 - 9 Between the years 1779 and 1813, the diminution of sick and of deaths in the British navy was in the proportion of four to one. In 1779, 1:2.45 were sick, and in 1813, 1:10.75 were sick, corresponding to decline by ratio 4.4. Table 1, p.539-540 in:
Blane G (1815) Statements of the comparative Health of the British Navy, from the year 1779 to the year 1814.
<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC2129027>

Biographies of Thomas Stevens

[https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Thomas_Stephens_\(Jesuit\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Thomas_Stephens_(Jesuit))

<https://www.jstor.org/stable/607122>

[https://en.wikisource.org/wiki/Catholic_Encyclopedia_\(1913\)/Thomas_Stephens](https://en.wikisource.org/wiki/Catholic_Encyclopedia_(1913)/Thomas_Stephens)

This below extract of Stevens' letter is from pages 237-238 in:
Southwood, J. (1924). Thomas Stephens, S. J., the First Englishman in India.
Bulletin of the School of Oriental Studies, University of London, 3(2), 231–240.
<https://www.jstor.org/stable/607122>

... after we had

lost ances, hoising up the sailes for to get the ship a coast in some safer place, or when it should please God, it pleased his mercy suddenly, where no man looked for helpe, to fill our sailes with wind from the land, & so we escaped, thanks be to God. And the day following, being in the place where they are alwayes wont to catch fish, we also fell a fishing, and so many they tooke, that they served all the ship for that day, and part of the next. And one of them pulled up a corall of great bignesse and price. For there they say (as we saw by experience) that the corals doe grow in the maner of stalks upon the rocks in the bottome, and waxe hard and red. **The day of perill was the nine and twentieth of July.** And you shall understand that, the Cape passed, there be two wayes to India: one within the Ile of S. Laurence, which they take willingly, because they refresh themselves at Mosambique a fortnight or a moneth, not without great need, and thence in a moneth more land in Goa. The other is without the Ile of S. Laurence, which they take when they set foorth so late, and come so late to the point, that they have no time to take the foresayd Mosambique, and then they goe heavily, because in this way

they take no port. **And by reason of the long navigation, and want of food and water, they fall into sundry diseases, their gummes waxe great, and swell, and they are faine to cut them away,¹⁰ their legges swell, and all the body becommeth sore, and so benumbed, that they can not stirre hand nor foot, and so they die for weaknesse, others fall into fluxes and agues, and die thereby.** And this way it was our chance to make: yet

10 Cutting of gums was described also by Jean de Joinville during the Seventh Crusade (1249):

“The sickness became much more severe throughout the camp, and the proud flesh in our men’s mouths grew to such excess that the barber-surgeons were obliged to cut it off, to give them a chance of chewing their food or swallowing anything. It was piteous to hear through the camp the shrieks of the people who were being operated upon for proud flesh, for they shrieked like women in childbirth.”

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17341537>

In the journal of Vasco da Gama’s first voyage (1497-1499) the swelling of gums was described as follows: “Many of our men fell ill here, their feet and hands swelling, and their gums growing over their teeth, so that they could not eat.” (p.21)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17781205>

In the journal of Magellan’s circumnavigation (1519-1522) the swelling of gums was described as follows: “But above all other calamities this was the worst: in some men the gums grew over the teeth, both lowers and uppers, so that they could not eat in any way and thus they died of this sickness.”

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC1806596>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18001193>

though we had more then one hundred and fifty sicke, there died not past seven and twenty; which losse they esteemed not much in respect of other times. Though some of ours were diseased in this sort yet, thanks be to God, I had my health all the way, contrary to the expectation of many: God send me my health so well in the land, if it may be to his honour and service. This way is full of privy rockes and quicke-sands, so that sometimes we durst not saile by night, but by the providence of God we saw nothing, nor never found bottome untill we came to the coast of India. When we had passed againe the line, and were come to the third degree or somewhat more, we saw crabs swimming on the water that were red as though they had bene sodden: but this was no signe of land. After, about the eleventh degree, the space of many dayes, more then ten thousand fishes by estimation followed round about our ship, whereof we caught so many, that for fifteene dayes we did eate nothing els, and they served our turne very well: for at this time we had neither meat nor almost any thing els to eate, our navigation growing so long that it drew neere to seven moneths, where as commonly they goe it in five, I meane when they saile the inner way. But these fishes were not signe of land, but rather of deepe sea.

...

If God send me my health, I shall have opportunity to write to you once againe. Now the length of my letter compelleth me to take my leave: and thus I wish your most prosperous health. From Goa the tenth of November, 1579.

Your loving sonne,
THOMAS STEVENS.